

MISCELLANEOUS RESULTS AND THEOREMS ON SMARANDACHE TERMS AND FACTOR PARTITIONS

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ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION (SFP) , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r) = F'(N)$,where

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

Also for the case

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_r = \dots = \alpha_n = 1$$

we denote

$$F(\underbrace{1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots}_{n \text{ - ones}}) = F(1\#n)$$

In [2] we define $b_{(n,r)} x(x-1)(x-2) \dots (x-r+1)(x-r)$ as the r^{th}

SMARANDACHE TERM in the expansion of

$$x^n = b_{(n,1)} x + b_{(n,2)} x(x-1) + b_{(n,3)} x(x-1)(x-2) + \dots + b_{(n,n)} x^n$$

In this note some more results depicting how closely the coefficients of the **SMARANDACHE TERM** and **SFPs** are related.

are derived.

DISCUSSION:

Result on the $[i^j]$ matrix:

Theorem (9.1) in [2] gives us the following result

$$x^n = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^x P_r a_{(n,r)} \quad \text{which leads us to the following}$$

beautiful result.

$$\sum_{k=1}^x k^n = \sum_{k=1}^x \sum_{r=1}^k {}^k P_r a_{(n,r)}$$

In matrix notation the same can be written as follows for $x = 4 = n$.

$$\begin{bmatrix} {}^1 P_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ {}^2 P_1 & {}^2 P_2 & 0 & 0 \\ {}^3 P_1 & {}^3 P_2 & {}^3 P_3 & 0 \\ {}^4 P_1 & {}^4 P_2 & {}^4 P_3 & {}^4 P_4 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 & 7 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1^1 & 1^2 & 1^3 & 1^4 \\ 2^1 & 2^2 & 2^3 & 2^4 \\ 3^1 & 3^2 & 3^3 & 3^4 \\ 4^1 & 4^2 & 4^3 & 4^4 \end{bmatrix}$$

In general

$$P * A' = Q \quad \text{where } P = \begin{bmatrix} {}^i P_j \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} \quad \text{-----(10.1)}$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{(i,j)} \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} \quad \text{and} \quad Q = \begin{bmatrix} i^j \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n}$$

(A' is the transpose of A)

Consider the expansion of x^n , again

$$x^n = b_{(n,1)} x + b_{(n,2)} x(x-1) + b_{(n,3)} x(x-1)(x-2) + \dots + b_{(n,n)} xP_n$$

for $x = 3$ we get

$$x^3 = b_{(3,1)} x + b_{(3,2)} x(x-1) + b_{(3,3)} x(x-1)(x-2)$$

comparing the coefficient of powers of x on both sides we get

$$b_{(3,1)} - b_{(3,2)} + 2 b_{(3,3)} = 0$$

$$b_{(3,2)} - 3 b_{(3,3)} = 0$$

$$b_{(3,3)} = 1$$

In matrix form

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} * \begin{bmatrix} b_{(3,1)} \\ b_{(3,2)} \\ b_{(3,3)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_3 * A_3 = B_3$$

$$A_3 = C_3^{-1} \cdot B_3$$

$$C_3^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(C_3^{-1})' = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

similarly it has been observed that

$$(C_4^{-1})' = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 7 & 6 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The above observation leads to the following theorem.

THEOREM (10.1)

In the expansion of x^n as

$$x^n = b_{(n,1)} x + b_{(n,2)} x(x-1) + b_{(n,3)} x(x-1)(x-2) + \dots + b_{(n,n)} {}^xP_n$$

If C_n be the coefficient matrix of equations obtained by equating the coefficient of powers of x on both sides then

$$(C_n^{-1})' = \left[a_{(i,j)} \right]_{n \times n} = \text{star matrix of order } n$$

PROOF: It is evident that C_{pq} the element of the p^{th} row and q^{th} column of C_n is the coefficient of x^p in xP_q . And also C_{pq} is independent of n . The coefficient of x^p on the RHS is coefficient of $x^p = \sum_{q=1}^n b_{(n,q)} C_{pq}$, also

coefficient of $x^p = 1$ if $p = n$

coefficient of $x^p = 0$ if $p \neq n$.

in matrix notation

$$\begin{aligned} \text{coefficient of } x^p &= \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{q=1}^n b_{(n,q)} C_{pq} \\ \phantom{\sum_{q=1}^n} \\ \phantom{\sum_{q=1}^n} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{q=1}^n b_{(n,q)} C'_{qp} \\ \phantom{\sum_{q=1}^n} \\ \phantom{\sum_{q=1}^n} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

$$= i_{np} \text{ where } i_{np} = 1, \text{ if } n = p \text{ and } i_{np} = 0, \text{ if } n \neq p.$$

$$= I_n \text{ (identity matrix of order } n.)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{(n,q)} \\ \phantom{b_{(n,q)}} \\ \phantom{b_{(n,q)}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{p,q} \\ \phantom{C_{p,q}} \\ \phantom{C_{p,q}} \end{bmatrix} = I_n$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{(n,q)} \\ \phantom{a_{(n,q)}} \\ \phantom{a_{(n,q)}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{p,q} \\ \phantom{C_{p,q}} \\ \phantom{C_{p,q}} \end{bmatrix} = I_n \quad \text{as } b_{(n,q)} = a_{(n,q)}$$

$$A_n \cdot C_n' = I_n$$

$$A_n \cdot = I_n [C_n']^{-1}$$

$$A_n \cdot = [C_n']^{-1}$$

This completes the proof of theorem (10.1).

THEOREM (10.2)

If $C_{k,n}$ is the coefficient of x^k in the expansion of xP_n , then

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F(1\#k) C_{k,n} = 1$$

PROOF: In property (3) of the STAR TRIANGLE following proposition has been established.

$F'(1\#n) = \sum_{m=1}^n a_{(n,m)} = B_n$, in matrix notation the same can be expressed as follows for $n = 4$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 3 & 7 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 6 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 & B_2 & B_3 & B_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

In general

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n} * \begin{bmatrix} a_{(i,j)} \\ (C_n^{-1})' \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} B_i \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_i \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n} * \begin{bmatrix} \\ (C_n) \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n}$$

In $C_{n,n}$, $C_{p,q}$ the p^{th} row and q^{th} column is the coefficient of x^p in xP_q . Hence we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F(1\#k) C_{k,n} = 1 = \sum_{k=1}^n B_k C_{k,n}$$

THEOREM(10.3)

$$\sum_{k=1}^n F(1\#(k+1)) C_{k,n} = n + 1 = \sum_{k=1}^n B_{k+1} C_{k,n}$$

PROOF:

It has already been established that

$$B_{n+1} = \sum_{m=1}^n (m+1) a_{(n,m)}$$

In matrix notation

$$\begin{bmatrix} j+1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n} * \begin{bmatrix} a_{(i,j)} \\ \vdots \\ (C_n^{-1}) \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{j+1} \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} j+1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{j+1} \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}_{1 \times n} * \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \vdots \\ (C_n) \end{bmatrix}_{n \times n}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n B_{k+1} C_{k,n} = n + 1$$

There exist ample scope for more such results.

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